

Modeling, synthesis and 3D printing of tube vocal tract models with a codeless graphical user interface

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Abstract

Calculating and predicting formants have many uses in speech-centric science. However, a significant imposition to widespread use across phonetics is the lack of accessible programs. In particular, students and scientists in phonetics often have little training in computational sciences or programming languages. We present the *TubeN* graphical user interface (GUI), a coherent speech acoustics software environment for modeling tube vocal tract models, including the ability to synthesize utterances, illustrate vocal tract transfer functions, and produce 3D-printable files for use outside the virtual environment. The program is publicly accessible and can be run without using code.

Introduction

This text serves the double purpose of (i) introducing the program and graphical user interface (GUI) to a speech-centric audience, and (ii) serving as user manual for this first published version of the program. The following sections describe each of the GUIs main functionalities, divided into three subsections. First, the historical, algorithmic, and computational bases of the implemented formant prediction procedure are described with reference to published formant data from real-life speakers. In the second section, functionalities of the GUI are described, including instructions on how to generate tube model sequences, synthesize

vowel sounds based on user input data, generate illustrations of vocal tract transfer functions corresponding to the input model, and generate 3D-printable files for inspection and use outside of the software environment. The third subsection describes how tube sequences created in the GUI may be 3D printed and the sound physically realized. We argue that *TubeN* can serve as a valuable teaching tool in speech-centric hearing sciences.

TubeN

Tube modelling

The vocal tract as tube

The idea of the vocal tract as a tube is several hundreds of years old. It was idea was arguably first tested in proper by the German physicist Christian Gottlieb Kratzenstein, who invented a “vowel organ” to test the “tonal differences between the five vowels A, E, I, O and U” – a prompt issued by the academy in Saint Petersburg in 1778. Kratzenstein’s organ, now lost, possessed a set of pipes, with each pipe corresponding to a unique resonance quality for each vowel sound (Story, 2019). The modern application of the concept, however, owes its form to the descriptions of the physical aspects of speech by Chiba and Kajiyama (1942) and to the circuit theory established by Fant (1970) through publication of his seminal work in *The acoustic theory of speech production*.

The Liljencrants-Fant algorithm

In their 1975 publication, *Computer program for VT-resonance frequency calculations*, Liljencrants and Fant (1975) introduced a program for algorithmically deriving vocal tract resonances based on the circuit theory and wall effects by Fant (1972). The method derives vocal tract resonance frequencies from area functions of tube representations of vocal tracts, based on volume-velocity glottal-lip transfer. Such vocal tract tube models, assuming rigid rounded structures cannot realistically capture intricate acoustic properties of flesh, cartilage, bone, and viscosity that make up real-life vocal tracts. However, their proper implementation allows for principled variation of parameters affecting properties of filtered voice signals.

TubeN reintroduces the program, and provide a use case for illustrating its potential use by researchers. The code supplied in the original publication has been converted into Python and made publicly available online. As in the original program, the user may manually input the number and lengths $A(N)$, and section areas of tubes $L(N)$; the shape of the resultant model is then graphically rendered, and – new to *TubeN* – resultant formant frequencies may be automatically synthesized as .wav files (using a static vowel formant synthesis, *formantsynt*), which can be used to inspect by ear the vowel qualities resulting from the given vocal tract shape. The user may also select the number of predicted formants. Because the mathematical bases of the program have been retained from the original publication (Liljencrants & Fant, 1975), they will not be described here: interested parties are referred to the original publication, and the available code.

Randomized sequences

To provide an illustration of how *TubeN* may be used by researchers, we computed vocal tract area transfer functions

for tubes corresponding to formant values observed for “point vowels” [a], [i] and [u] (the vowels in “ma”, “boot”, and “see”, respectively), corresponding to extremities of articulatory space. We targeted vowel formants for Swedish vowels reported by Fant et al. (1969). Using *TubeN*, we then computed a set of 50,000 randomized sequences of tubes, varying only VT area transfer function configurations, and holding the lengths of the four tubes constant at 2 cm, 6 cm, 6 cm, and 2 cm (corresponding to a total VT length of 16 cm). We then computed best fit based on predicted first, second, and third formant frequencies (F1, F2, F3). Tube segments are summarized in Table 1, formants are summarized in Table 2. The exercise confirmed the appropriateness of the method for its intended purposes. The code has also been used in previous published works (Ekström & Edlund, 2024).

Table 1. Four-tube sequences generated through the “brute force” method.

Vowel	Area(s) (cm ²)				
[a]	2.0	5.0	0.2	0.2	2.0
[i]	2.0	0.2	5.0	5.0	2.0
[u]	0.1	5.0	1.0	1.0	2.0

Functionalities

Example settings

Vocal tract configurations for [a i u] were derived from Fant (1970) and implemented as example settings. These configurations can be implemented with single clicks directly from the GUI.

Add

The *Add* button allows the user to type in lengths and areas of a tube or sequence of tubes. An interactive schematic diagram of the tube is displayed and updated with every new segment added (Figure 1). Alternatively, the program can read a text file, wherein lengths and areas of segments are provided.

Remove

The *Remove* function allows the user to remove a given section. It can be executed by clicking a segment and using the clickable *Remove* button.

Alter

The *Alter* command changes the size and area of any individual section. To execute, the user clicks any given tube section, clicks the clickable *Alter* button, and types in the new length and area number.

Scale

The *Scale* command enables the user to linearly scale the input tube sequence, maintaining proportionally appropriate relationships between tube segments. The scaling command can be executed either by clicking up or down on the appropriate small black triangle button of the Double Spin Box (the program scales in increments of .1 times the original sequences), or type in the desired scale change. The user executes the scaling by pressing the *Scale* button, generating a new tube sequence. The scaling algorithm scales the entirety of the tube sequence linearly, such that sections remain proportional.

Table 2. Vowel formants for adult male native Swedish speakers speaking [a i u] (Fant et al., 1969), and closest fit for each computed by random four-tube sequences.

Vowel	Fant et al.	<i>TubeN</i>
[a]	F1 = 600	F1 = 592
	F2 = 925	F2 = 960
	F3 = 2540	F3 = 2817
[i]	F1 = 255	F1 = 256
	F2 = 2190	F2 = 2199
	F3 = 3150	F3 = 2986
[u]	F1 = 290	F1 = 276
	F2 = 595	F2 = 668
	F3 = 2330	F3 = 2629

Obliviate

The *Obliviate* command empties current input and removes the implemented tube sequence, allowing users to start anew.

Speech synthesis

Synthesis

The *Generate Sound* button synthesizes a .wav audio file based on the current tube information. To avoid naming conflict problems, each audio is for a timestamp (the time it is created), in the format of hour-minute-second (e.g., 15-50-56.wav). In this first iteration of the program, vowels are synthesized with a constant $f_0 = 100$ Hz and a length of 1 s.

Trajectory

The *Trajectory* command allows users to synthesize formant transitions (“ai”, “au”, etc.). Users can manually input anchor values or select from a provided F1-F2 vowel space.

Play

The user can inspect the synthetic sound by pressing the “play” button. Upon synthesis, the file is automatically saved in .wav format to the user’s hard drive.

Illustration

The *Illustrate* button is used to plot the Tube model, peak function and area transfer function. The plot is displayed on the Graphics View widget, which opens as a new window (Figure 3). Illustrations are automatically saved to the user’s hard drive with a .png file-name extension.

3D printing

The *3D File* button creates a 3D-printable (.stl) file based on the current input. Users may then slice the file with settings of the desired 3D printer in order to customize the relevant G-code and print the tube using methods derived from Trimesh Python library (<https://trimesh.org/>). We have sought to make this process as straightforward as possible:

details of this procedure is described in an accompanying .pdf manual.

Continuous model

We sought to 3D-print a generated tube model as a single consistent object, from a single .stl file. This is achieved by reusing and connecting single tube sections, and each section is made by subtracting a cylinder from a larger unit. In this manner, differences between tube areas are straightforwardly sealed by adding a “lid” in between, and without additional modeling. A “continuous” model provides a realization of the GUI-constructed tube and, in demonstrations, proved to reliably reproduce the intended vowel quality (in these demonstrations, a duck call was used as a substitute for the voice source). A “continuous” model printed after the “[i] tube” design seen in Figures 1 and 3, can be seen in Figure 4. As a note of caution, we observed that in printing our “continuous” models, in order to maintain the balance of the whole structure while printing, extra support material had to be generated inside the tube by the printer software; in some cases, these additions were manually removable after printing. We found that this problem could be avoided by printing models “standing up”, rather than on the side.

Detachable model

As an extension, we also sought to test the potential for “detachable” models – an effectively “LEGO-like” design where sections can be assembled and re-assembled after printing. In this explorative build, each section was made into a separate .stl file. A significant potential downside to this approach was that, in order to maintain the ability to assemble the build in different orders, the outwardly observable size of the whole model had to be kept constant (to maintain fit with other segments); in our attempts, this was determined by the largest input tube section. In this manner, printed sections are effectively reusable;

and the approach does not suffer from the issue of interference from structural support elements. We aim to further explore the potential for “reusable” tube sections in future iterations.

3D printing: Additional considerations

For 3D printing, we used a Prusa i3 MK3 3D printer. The material used was Polyactic Acid (PLA). The observations reported here for physical models are based on experience with these products only. Because 3D printers may use a range or different materials, we cannot categorically state that any settings are appropriate for printing tube sequences; other available materials may be more or less appropriate. A continuous model normally took 2.5 hours to print, while a detachable model (all four sections) took approximately 4.5 hours. The printer software handles placement and generates the necessary support automatically. If available, we recommend the use of water-dissolvable material for support.

Discussion

The *TubeN* software and GUI may be used as a complement in phonetics classes. The code and GUI .exe file, are publicly available for download. In future work, we intend to investigate and evaluate the potential of the *TubeN* environment for phonetics and speech acoustics teaching (e.g., Arai, 2022). We believe exploring relationships of speech acoustics is a valuable method of instruction and learning. In future work, we intend to investigate and evaluate the potential of the *TubeN* environment for phonetics and speech acoustics teaching. We hope that introducing a codeless and easily accessible environment facilitates phonetics learning for a new generation of students: we encourage teachers of phonetics to explore such an endeavor with us. The code and GUI .exe file, are publicly available for download (github.com/jbeskow/tuben).

Figure 1. The new realization of the computer program by Liljencrants and Fant (1975), with a codeless graphical user interface. The program can be run without any coding experience using an executable .exe file, available in the relevant GitHub repository.

Figure 2. The “Trajectory” window. Graphical vowel space of Canadian vowels from Russell (2024).

Figure 3. Four-tube illustration for the example [i]. The new realization of the computer program by Liljencrants and Fant (1975) includes code for generating illustrations of distance from lips (top), spectral peak determinants (middle), and vocal tract area transfer functions (bottom) for sequences of tubes.

Figure 4. A 3D printed tube section. After the example model presented in Liljencrants and Fant (1975). The configuration is the same as in Figures 1 and 3. Total length is 16 cm. The tube is positioned top-down as corresponding to increasing distance from the lips.

Acknowledgements

The results of this work will be more widely accessible through the national infrastructure Språkbanken Tal under funding from the Swedish Research Council (2017-00626).

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